

Land Revenue in the Chola Period 850-1238 CE

K. Packiyalakshmi,

Ph.D, Research Scholar, Department of History,
V. O. Chidambaram College, Thoothukudi-628008.
Mobile No: 9025542590, E-mail Id; packiya11111@gmail.com.

Prof. P. Tharumar,

Associate professor
Department of History, V. O. Chidambaram College,
Thoothukudi-628008.

A B S T R A C T

The Cholas ruled over South India for more than a thousand years. Emperors ruled throughout this time, and due to the size of the Empire, local government received a lot of attention. Local government in cities and villages, justice, and land revenue were all organised during the Chola period. Because young boys chose the representatives using a lottery system, the local government was democratic. The Chola government has been acknowledged as the foundation of modern democracy.

Key Words: Cholas ruled, Empire, Local government, Justice, Democracy, Inscriptions

Introduction

This chapter seeks to analyse the rates of land tax of the Chola period with a view to quantify the land revenue of the Chola state. The data for this study comes from inscriptions mostly relating to land grants to temples which specify some tax remissions in favour of the temples. In most of these cases the remissions were made by the king (and rarely by a chief in Period 1 and in others by some local bodies like the sabha and the like. In the latter cases, the local bodies undertook the responsibility of paying themselves the remitted tax to the government. The data is presented in Table 8.1, the available 'Cases' arranged chronologically. The rates are given as so many kalam per veli (k/v). Kalam is the standard grain measure. The subunits below kalam have been converted into decimal fractions of kalam (rounded to two decimals). In the case of land, the standard unit was vēli and its subunits. Here also the fractions are rounded to two decimals. In terms of modern units, a kalam of paddy is approximately 29 kilogram by weight and 1 veli is equal to 6.61 acres or 2.68 hectares. In the remarks column are given, wherever available, the specific terms which denoted the land tax in the concerned inscription. In some cases information about the nature of land (like nir-nilam wet land', and the like) on which the levy was made is given in the context to clarify. Though the primary land tax was generally denoted by the term ipai in the earlier half of the Chola rule, it was also denoted in many contexts by the term kanik-kadan, meaning 'the dues on kami. It is also qualified in some cases by the adjectival participle inai-katina to specify. This article was previously published in *Level Revenue Assessment under the Cholas An Exercise at Clio*, in *Indian History Congress Proceedings, Stat Sess Calcutta, 1991*. On to are the dues paid towards the government tax. In some contexts this elective alone denoted the land tax (for example, ipai-hatina nella the paddy paid towards the government tax). The other terms which denoted the land tax were Kadamai mel-varam opani (from

Sanskrit nis, and, in one case, nigdymai. The term Kademe became the norm in the latter half. A careful contextual analysis is before necessary to clarify the problem. (The specific context is elaines briefly in the explanatory notes on the data.) Regarding the spatial distribution of the data, it seems to be centrated mainly in the districts of Tanjavur and Tiruchirappalli and so some extent in South Arcot also. These districts comprised the central area of the Chola state. There is only one instance each for worth Arcot and Chengalpattu District. The poor representation in the outlying areas may have something to do with the nature of the Chola government there. Period-wise, the distribution is somewhat even for the later three periods. For Period 1 (850-985 CE), the number is smaller because instances start appearing only from its latter half.

Deviation

From the cases of Period 1, it may be suggested that for good (standard) land the normal rate was 120 k/v. In Case 4, it is said that the original extent of land was 15 veli and that this 15 v. (of ordinary land) was calculated as 3 v. of madakku land. The term madakku denoted a notional 'standard' land. The rate 120 k/v was applied only this standard land.¹ In other cases, the land is not specified as such, perhaps because those lands already had the minimum requirements for treating them as 'standard' lands. In some cases there is, however, me deviation from the normal rate, either a little more (Case 5) or a little less (Case 1). The lower rate in Case I may be due to a partial mission on dévadana land. This fact is clear from Cases

With the accession of Rajaraja I (985-1014 CE) the standard of 100kly seems to have come into vogue. Rajaraja I is known for many administrative innovations and this might also

¹K.A Nilakandasasthiri The Chola, University of Madras, 1955.

be one of them. The first systematic countrywide land survey was made from his sixteenth year (1001) and it may be suggested that the land survey might have made the application of that rate easier throughout the country. once all the details of land were properly recorded. It has, however many inscriptions, the actual details regarding classification of lands be mentioned that even though the land survey is mentioned in. That the rate of 100 k/v applied only to the lands producing two Are not available in them. tops annually a) has been clarified by Karashima. by a comparative study of the land revenue details of several villages given in two Tanjavur inscriptions of Rajaraja 1 with those given in a 1069 ce inscription from Gangaikondacholapuram (Cases 12 and 20). Some slight deviations from this standard rate found in the rates of some villages are due to mixing up of some single-crop or dry-crop lands along with the double-crop lands in those villages.

Once established, the standard of 100 k/v had a long currency as it recurs as late as 1238 CE. But rates varied widely in the case which deviated from the standard norms and this is known from the study of the Gangaikondacholapuram inscription." It is known from this inscription that productivity of the lands of the same category differed from locality to locality. In fact, outside the fertile Kaveri delta, lands were of very low productivity due to poor rain and precarious irrigation facilities and consequently the rates also had to be very low.

Case 14 relating to the (average) rates in some fifty-four villages in Papanasam Taluk of Tanjavur District illustrates this point clearly. Half of these villages produced a rate less than 20 k/v and some reaching to the ludicrously low level of 1 or 2 k/v. These are actually rates for dry-crop lands. The above villages were all situated on the southern fringes of the Kaveri delta and so could not draw water from the Kaveri canals at that time." They had only rain-fed tanks for irrigation purposes.

Tentatively, therefore, it may be suggested that the rate of 100 kalam plus or minus applied to river-irrigated paddy lands raising two crops annually. For other paddy lands irrigated by tanks or wells the rates generally ranged between 20 and 50 k/v.² Rates less than 20 k/v must have related generally to dry-crop lands.

The government normally lost its tax revenue from lands assigned to temples or other eleemosynary bodies as the land tax was transferred for the enjoyment of the donees (temple, sabha, and such others). But this 'tax remission' seems in most cases to be only partial. That is, the so-called tax-free lands (iraiyili) had to pay some portion of the original land dues to the government. In pre-Chola times and even in the first century of (Period 1) of the Chola rule, and rarely thereafter, this reduced or concessional rate was called pañcha-num or one-fifth share. Strictly speaking, the pañcha-varam should be 1/5th of the full land tax. In Periods 3 and 4 this concessional rate was denoted by the phrase nichchayitta opāti, that is, 'the due that is determined'. The new rate is a kind of arbitrary determination. It was about 60 per cent of the original and sometimes it may be as was 40 per cent (Case 21). This reduction to 60 per cent is also indicated by another phrase partārākki meaning to convert 10 into 6. But in some cases the original rates that the temples were paying were lower. For instance, in Case 33 the original rates were 40.8 k/v and 39.29 k/v, respectively, and in 1145 these two rates were changed 100 k/v (quite arbitrarily) and then 60 per cent of it, that is, 60 We was fixed as the government dues. Usually this happened when de concerned land was transferred from one donee to another. The mmakkalam and frikariyapperu used in certain late inscriptions lases 48, 50, and 52) also seem to denote the concessional rate. seems to suggest that one-third of the total tax was paid to the government, the rest being retained by the temple.

² P.Shanmugam, The revenue System of the chola,850-1279,New era publication, Madras,1987.

Revenue of the Chōla government

From the foregoing information some idea can be had as to the nature and volume of the land revenue of the Chōla government. Naturally, the bulk of the revenue should have come from the Kaveri delta which was the core area of the Chola state. There was, therefore, concentration of royal and official activities in the delta³. It is possible that the government lost some of its income from the villages or lands assigned to temples, Brahmanas, and the like. But this loss was never 100 per cent; generally it was 40 to 50 per cent of the full rate. In the case of the Brahmana settlements, most of them seem to have paid full tax in Periods 3 and 4 (Case 38). Actually at times the Brahmana landlords suffered like everybody else due to heavy tax burden and they had consequently to resort to distress sale of their lands. Moreover, only about 10 to 15 per cent of the villages in the delta were either brahmadeya or devadana and so the loss of the revenue would be at the most 15 per cent only.

Estimate the land revenue

To estimate the total annual land revenue of the Chola government, we need more statistics than that available now regarding the total under cultivation and also the nature and productivity of the lands in different settlements. On a rough estimate it has been found that there were 1,300 villages in Chola-mandalam and Naduvil-nadu (Tanjavur, Tiruchirappalli, and South Arcot districts) of which about data provided by cases 12, 14, 20, and 21 it seems that an average 1,000 were vellanvagai villages paying full assessments. From the element had about 40 veli of assessed land. If this average extent taken as a mixture of both double- and single-crop lands, it would pay to the government about 3,000 kalam of paddy annually. And million kalam, that is, about 87,000 metric tonnes (treating kalam , for the 1,000 settlements

³ South Indian inscriptions Vol.iv.

the total yield would be nearly three lagesen in 2 and-crop tency the from egory Kaven and mad to point and are Tufted draw min-fed of 100 raising rwelk han 20 ssigned sferred others).That rations of mess and ad rarely hound be tonal rate due that mention may be as as equal to 29 kilograms by weight). There were, of course, som exceptionally big settlements such as Alangudi of Case 38 paying huge quantity by themselves. Such villages were, however, exceptineal and very few⁴

Collection of the land tax

As to the mode of collection of the land tax, there is some informati available. The paddy dues seem to have been collected in two instalment in a year: one during the kar (short-term) crop (harvested in September February) and the other during the pasanam (long-term) crop (harved in January/February) (for example, Case 38). The accounting year w counted to begin from the pasanam season.

Commuted in money generally until Period

The rate in grain was not commuted in money generally until Period 4. Only in the case of mercantile settlements money rates were applied. Outside the Chola-mandalam the money-rates seem to have been applied in the case of ordinary villages too. There is some evidence to suggest that in Chola-mandalam to the land tax was partly commuted in money during the fag end of the Chola rule

Finally, to answer the question what proportion of the land produce was taken away by the government we have very little explicit information. In a Kolar District inscription (Case 56), it is said that 1/3 went to the government on tank-irrigated paddy lands and 1/5 for

⁴ P.Shanmugam, The revenue System of the chola,850-1279,New era publication,Madras,1987.

dry lands. But here we do not have the actual quantity of the produce to compare this rate with that from other places. Moreover this kind of paying a share of the produce, gross or net, does not seem to be popular. There is another inscription from the Tanjavur District (Case 57) which provides some interesting information about the ground rent paid to the landlords by their tenants. It is said that the Brahmana landlords received as rent $\frac{2}{3}$ of the net produce, that is the gross produce less cultivation expenses. Other landlords (temples Vellala, and others) took $\frac{3}{5}$ of the gross produce leaving $\frac{2}{5}$ to the cultivators and the latter had to bear the cultivating expenses out of their (cultivator's) share (kudi-varam). In the same village, there followed another mode of rent payment, that is, to pay a fixed quantity annually. This fixed rent herein referred to as kadamai ranged from 160 to 320 k/v for first grade land (talai varisa) and from 80 to 150 k/v for single-crop land.⁵ Unfortunately, what proportion of this rent was paid as land tax is not mentioned in the inscription. If, for once the middle rate of 240 k/v is taken as rent for the first grade land and if the tax is taken as 100 k/v then about 40 per cent of rent would have been paid as tax. In Case no. 15, mêlvānum is fixed at 50 per cent of the varisai (rent).

Conclusion

King gifted irai on 10 veli of land to temple. The commutation value is given at 8 kalam to a madai. Case. This Pandya inscription is given here for the sake of comparison. It is similar to, but more elaborate .Out of the total quantity of 60 kalam decided for the rent paid by the cultivators of the devadana land 40 kalam goes to the temple and 20 to the government (pandaram). The land was given by an individual to temple. It is said that the income from the land was to be given to temple after deducting the pañcha-varam (obviously dues meant

⁵ Y.Suburayulu South India under the Cholas, Oxford university,2012.

for the government). If one kalanju is taken to be equivalent to 10 kalam approximately, then the rate for pancha-varam in this case would work out to 23 k/v. But the paddy value of a kalañju varied from 7 to 16 kalam during the tenth to eleventh centuries. The land was an old archana-bhoga and now it was purchased by a merchant for endowing it to another charity. The merchant was permitted to utilize the income from the land after paying off the pancha-varam which is said to be the due that was to be paid (to the government) after excluding the income to deity (devarkku nikki irukkak kadava). Similar to previous case Pancha-varam is here called as irai.

This well-known inscription records a decision of the supra-local assembly of agriculturalists called patinenbhumi-periya vishayam (same as chittiramēli-periya-nādu) regarding the share (varam) they had to pay as government tax. But it is not clear on what basis (whether it was the gross produce or net government share was decided. Besides the two items given in the table the inscription also refers to the tax on the kummari (swidden crop) lands at the rate of one basketful of grain per 1,500 kufi (0.75 veli). As the inscription is very fragmentary full details are produce) the not ascertainable. This seems to be a forerunner of the one given in.

Reference:

1. Noboru karashima, South India History and society: Study From inscription, AD 850-1800,Oxford University Press, New Delhi,1984.
2. P.Shanmugam, The revenue System of the chola,850-1279, New era publication,Madras,1987.
3. K.A Nilakandasasthiri The Chola,University of Madras, 1955.
4. Y.Suburayulu South India under the Cholas, Oxford university,2012.
5. South Indian inscriptions Vol.iv.